

Review Article

Multi-Targeted Therapeutic Effects of *Mimusops Elengi*: A Natural Remedy for Chronic Diseases

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-diabetic activities, and bioactive compounds by using GCMS and nutrient analysis of *Mimusops Elengi* leaves was performed. *Mimusops Elengi* leaves were tested for their anti-inflammatory activity by using the heat-induced hemolysis method. Antioxidant activity was evaluated using the DPPH assay, and the α -amylase test was performed to investigate the anti-diabetic activity. Identification of bioactive compounds by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and nutrient analysis was done by the AOAC method. *Mimusops elengi* leaf extract showed strong in vitro anti-inflammatory activity, outperforming diclofenac with a scavenging activity of 47.57 μ g/mL. At 250 μ L, it achieved 89.91% inhibition, increasing dose-dependently from 36.11% at 50 μ L. Its antioxidant activity was moderate, compared to rutin and BHT. Scavenging activity reached 60.53 μ g/mL, surpassing acarbose. GC-MS revealed bioactive compounds like diphenyl sulfone, ethyl ester, and squalene, suggesting applications in food, medicine, cosmetics, and industry. Nutrient analysis showed low fat, high in calcium, iron, vitamin A and crude fibre. *Mimusops elengi* contains phytochemicals like triterpenoids, flavones, gallic acid esters, and steroids. Its parts are used in traditional medicine for microbial issues, including inflammation, ulcers, stomach problems, diarrhea, gum disease, and sore lips.

Keywords: Antihyperlipidemic; Bioactive compounds; Diphenyl sulfone; Gallic acid esters

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Introduction

Plants are a vital part of human life, used for building, food, and medicine. Plant-based medicine formulations are used as fundamental healthcare remedies in many civilizations. Traditional medical systems like Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha use plants, either by themselves or in particular formulations, to treat a range of ailments [1]. The importance of natural substances in pharmaceutical biology is widely known. Plants have been used as a great source of medicine for thousands of years. For Hindus, *Mimusops elengi* is a sacred plant that plays a major role in religious works and ancient Sanskrit literature [2]. It is thought that medicinal plants are a significant source of novel chemicals with possible medical use. The research into plants with alleged folkloric use as pain relievers, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant [3].

Free radical damage is caused by unstable, extremely reactive atoms or molecules that have unpaired electrons. According to the symptoms of oxidative stress, Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) are thought to have a role in the pathogenesis of numerous diseases, including aging, cancer, coronary heart disease, Alzheimer's disease, neurological disorders, atherosclerosis, cataracts, and inflammation [4]. In both the food and medicinal industries, antioxidant research is a crucial area of study. Significant bioactive chemicals found in a variety of plant and dietary sources have drawn a lot of interest recently. ROS-induced oxidation can lead to DNA mutation, membrane protein damage, and cell membrane disintegration, all of which can further start or spread the development of numerous illnesses, including cancer, liver damage, and cardiovascular disease [5]. The current estimate of 150 million people with diabetes is expected to rise to 300 million by 2025, from 220 million in 2010 [6].

Mimusops elengi Linn (family Sapotaceae) is a tree native to the western peninsula of South India. It is also referred to as the Spanish cherry, Medlar, and Bullet wood in English. Many other Indian languages have acquired the term Bakul, which was used to refer to the tree in the ancient Sanskrit language. Ancient Indian texts such as the Ramayana, Mahabharata, Abhijnana Shakuntala, and Raghuvansha all make reference to the tree, demonstrating its significance in pre-historic times [7]. In South and central India, particularly in the woods of Madhya Pradesh, Jammu, Bihar, Mewad Awadh, and the Andaman Islands, it is grown [8].

Since every portion of *Mimusops elengi* L. is utilised in a different method to treat a range of human ailments, it is regarded as one of the best medicinal plants. The medication is described in Ayurveda as cooling, cardiogenic, alexipharmic, stomachic, anthelmintic, astringent, and it heals biliousness and gum and tooth diseases. In traditional medicine, an internal bark infusion is recommended for bladder and urethral diseases. It is thought that using a bark decoction to rinse the mouth may strengthen the gums, lessen inflammation, stop gum bleeding, and stop bad breath brought on by dental caries and pyorrhea.

The objective of this study (i) determine the *Mimusops elengi* in vitro antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic activity; (ii)

screen the bioactive compounds by using GCMS, which supports its pharmacological use; and (iii) analyse the nutrient composition of the leaves of *Mimusops Elengi's*, providing scientific proof of these benefits, bridging traditional wisdom with modern science and encouraging trust in natural remedies.

Materials and Methods

Selection and collection of *Mimusops Elengi*

M. elengi has been used in the Unani and other traditional systems of medicine for a long time. *M. elengi* were reported for treatment of several human ailments and the most of the parts of this plant is used in various ways to cure a variety of human disease like toothache, ulcer, fever, headache, palpitation, constipation, smallpox, cough, etc.... [9]. The leaves have been considered as an antidote for snakebite [10]. *Mimusops elengi* is a plant rich in bioactive compounds, offering promising pharmacological and therapeutic benefits. Its phytochemical composition, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, and saponins, contributes to its diverse medicinal properties [11].

Mimusops Elengi were collected in the village of Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu. The leaves should be tender and not be over matured. *Mimusops elengi* leaves were authenticated by scientist Dr. M.U.SHARIEF botanical survey of India, Coimbatore and letter no. BSI/SRC/5/23/2024-25/Tech./420.

In vitro Anti-Inflammatory Activity

Heat-Induced Hemolysis: The method had been previously described and slightly modified and followed. The reaction mixture (2ml) consisted of 1.0 ml of 10% HRBC and 1ml of various plant extract solvents (1mg/ml), which were added to each tube and gently mixed. The positive control consisted of 1.0ml of HRBC and 1.0ml of various concentrations of diclofenac sodium (10 to 50µg/ml). The negative control consisted of 1.0 ml of 10% erythrocyte suspension and 1.0ml of normal saline alone. The experiment was performed in triplicate. The resulting solution was heated at 56°C for 30 minutes, cooled to room temperature, and centrifuged at 2500rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was collected, and the absorbance of each solution was measured spectrophotometrically (UVmini 1240, Shimadzu) at 560nm as an indicator of the degree of haemolysis. The percentage inhibition of hemolysis was calculated using the formula (Plate No 1).

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{\text{Ac} - \text{At}}{\text{Ac}} \times 100$$

Where 'Ac' is the absorbance of the control and 'At' is the absorbance of the test.

Plate No 1: *Mimusops elengi* leaves.

In vitro Antioxidant Activity

DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity: The antioxidant activity of the extract was determined in terms of hydrogen-donating or radical-scavenging ability using the stable radical DPPH, according to the method of Blois (1958). Sample extracts at various concentrations were taken, and the volume was adjusted to 100µL with methanol. About 5mL of a 0.1mm methanolic solution of DPPH was added to the aliquots of samples and standards (BHA, BHT, rutin and quercetin) and shaken vigorously. Negative control was prepared by adding 100µL of methanol to 5mL of 0.1mM methanol solution DPPH. The tubes were allowed to stand for 20min at 27°C. The absorbance of the sample was measured at 517nm against the blank (methanol). Radical scavenging activity of the samples was expressed as IC50, which is the concentration of the sample required to inhibit 50% of DPPH concentration (Plate No 2).

Plate No 2: *Mimusops elengi* leaves.

In vitro anti-diabetic activity

Inhibition Assay for α-Amylase Activity: α-Amylase was premixed with extract at various concentrations (50-200µg/mL), and starch as a substrate was added (0.5% starch solution) to start the reaction. The reaction was carried out at 37°C for 5min and terminated by the addition of 2mL of DNS (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid) reagent. The reaction mixture was heated for 15min at 100°C and diluted with 10mL of distilled water in an ice bath. α-Amylase activity was determined by measuring the spectrum at 540nm. The IC50 value was defined as the concentration of α-amylase inhibitor to inhibit 50% of its activity under the assay conditions (Plate No 3).

Plate No 3: *Mimusops elengi* leaves.

GC-MS Test of *Mimusops Elengi* Leaves

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry is a popular analytical method for Determining Which Plant extracts contain bioactive substances. This work used GC-MS analysis to identify the phytochemical composition of leaf extracts from *Mimusops Elengi* leaves. This

method aids in the Detection of volatile and Semi-volatile substances, offering information on the pharmacological potential of the plant. Its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-diabetic effects are attributed to the presence of a variety of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and organic compounds. Mass spectrometry was used to identify the material after it was inserted into a column and separated according to molecular weight and polarity using a typical GC-MS system. A profile of the chemicals present was provided by the resulting chromatogram, and these were identified by comparison with spectrum databases that were already in existence.

Nutrient Analysis of *Mimusops Elengi* Leaves

Macronutrients such as fat, protein, carbohydrate, and crude fibre, as well as micronutrients like vitamin A, calcium, and iron, were assessed by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists' (AOAC) standard method. AOAC technique is a standard method and is widely trusted for its accuracy, in addition to ensuring reliability and consistency (Table 1).

Test Parameter/Standard	Method of Testing	Methodology	Reference
Energy Kcal/100g	IFS/C/STP/FC/008	NIN	IS 14433.2007 (RE-AFF.2012); Clause 6.10.1 C
Carbohydrate %	IFS/C/STP/FC/013	Colorimetric	Biochem J.1954 jul;57(3):508-514
Protein %	IS:7219-1973	Titrimetric	
Total fat %	IFS/C/STP/FC/012	Gravimetric	IS:4684:1975
Crude fiber %			AOAC 999.11
Vitamin A mg/100g	IFS/C/STP/AAS/004	AAS	AOAC 999.10 and AOAC 999.11
Iron mg/100g	IFS/C/STP/AAS/004	AAS	AOAC 999.10 and AOAC 999.11
Calcium mg/100g	IFS/C/STP/AAS/004	AAS	AOAC 999.10 and AOAC 999.11

Table 1: Methods used for nutrient analysis of *Mimusops Elengi* leaves.

Results and Discussion

In vitro Anti-Inflammatory Activity

Table 2, in the in vitro anti-inflammatory activity screening, it was observed that *M. elengi* extract showed significant activity when compared to the standard diclofenac. Heat-induced hemolysis activity in fresh *Mimusops Elengi* Leaves (25.40%, 39.89%, 54.59%, 65.56%, and 75.79%) and the standard diclofenac (47.43%, 51.05%, 56.38%, 63.71%, and 70.45%). The total % scavenging activity of fresh *Mimusops Elengi* Leaves is 47.57µg/mL, and the standard is 27.92µg/mL. Compared to standard diclofenac, fresh *Mimusops Elengi* leaves showed the best result in 250µl [12].The article indicates that the in vitro anti-inflammatory activity screening observed that *M. elengi* extract showed significant activity when compared to the standard diclofenac sodium. It indicates that the presence of phenolic content, good antioxidant properties (Figure 1).

In vitro Anti-Oxidant Activity

Table 3, the DPPH assay is widely used to evaluate the antioxidant potential of compounds by measuring their ability to donate

Extracts	% of Inhibition		% Scavenging Activity IC50 (µg/mL)
	Concentration (µl)	% Inhibition	
<i>Mimusops elengi</i>	50µl	25.40	47.57
	100µl	39.89	
	150µl	54.59	
	200µl	65.56	
	250µl	75.77	
Diclofenac	50µl	47.43	27.92
	100µl	51.05	
	150µl	56.38	
	200µl	63.71	
	250µl	70.45	

Table 2: Heat-Induced Hemolysis of *Mimusops Elengi*.

Figure 1: % of inhibition in *Mimusops Elengi* Leaves.

hydrogen and neutralize free radicals. *Mimusops elengi* extract exhibited a dose-dependent increase in percentage inhibition, with values ranging from 36.11% (50µL) to 89.91% (250µL). This trend indicates that higher concentrations of the extract contain more active compounds capable of scavenging free radicals. Rutin, a standard flavonoid, also displayed a concentration-dependent increase in inhibition, achieving the highest percentage (76.05%) at 25µL. BHT, a synthetic antioxidant, showed percentage inhibition from 18.89% (5µL) to 67.13% (25µL). The IC50 value represents the concentration required to achieve 50% inhibition of DPPH radicals. Lower IC50 values correspond to higher antioxidant activity. The IC50 of *Mimusops elengi* extract was 31.40µg/mL, indicating moderate antioxidant activity. Rutin exhibited the strongest antioxidant activity with an IC50 of 4.44µg/mL, demonstrating its effectiveness as a natural antioxidant. BHT had an IC50 of 5.56µg/mL, slightly higher than rutin, confirming its standard antioxidant potential. The antioxidant potential of *Mimusops elengi* was lower compared to rutin and BHT, as evidenced by its higher IC50 value. However, the extract still showed significant free radical scavenging activity, highlighting its potential as a source of natural antioxidants. According to [13]. The activity's results, *M. elengi* leaf methanol extract had a high total antioxidant capacity at 50 and 100µg (indicating that the absorbance of the total antioxidant capacity was so high that it exceeded the spectrophotometer's measurable range), and at 100µg, *M. elengi* leaf extract in dichloromethane (40µg) and leaf of n-hexane crude extract (24.4µg) (Figure 2).

In vitro Anti-Diabetic Activity

Table 4, depicts the ability of fresh *Mimusops Elengi* leaves to prevent diabetes. Fresh leaves of *Mimusops Elengi* with varying levels of α-amylase activity (25.52%, 38.65%, 44.21%, 51.45%, 65.33%) and

Extracts	% of Inhibition		% Scavenging Activity IC50 (µg/mL)
	Concentration (µL)	% Inhibition	
Mimusops elengi	50µl	36.11	31.40
	100µl	56.46	
	150µl	67.87	
	200µl	73.3	
	250µl	89.91	
	5µl	15.14	
Rutin	10µl	19.36	4.44
	15µl	36.61	
	20µl	59.97	
	25µl	76.05	
	5µl	18.89	
BHT	10µl	34.27	5.56
	15µl	44.71	
	20µl	63.84	
	25µl	67.13	
	5µl	15.14	

Table 3: DPPH radical scavenging activity of *Mimusops elengi* Leaves.

Acarbose (13.81%, 28.70%, 43.66%, 52.53%, 64.72%). Acarbose has a scavenging activity of 12.53 (µg/mL) while fresh *Mimusops elengi* leaves had a total of 60.53 (µg/mL). Based on the data, which was given in [14], it was concluded that the methanolic extract of *Mimusops elengi* significantly lowers blood glucose levels. The standard medication, Glimipride, was used to compare the solution's action. Comparably identical results are obtained from the plant extract in lowering albino rats' blood glucose levels. However, control does not have a favourable response to diabetes. The present study compares with the [14], article indicates that the Methanolic extract of *Mimusops elengi* significantly decreases the serum glucose level (Figure 3).

Extracts	% of Inhibition		% Scavenging Activity IC50 (µg/mL)
	Concentration (µL)	% Inhibition	
Mimusops elengi	50µl	25.52	60.53
	100µl	38.65	
	150µl	44.21	
	200µl	51.45	
	250µl	65.33	
Acarbose	10µl	13.81	12.53
	20µl	28.70	
	30µl	43.66	
	40µl	52.53	
	50µl	64.72	

Table 4: α-amylase Activity of *Mimusops elengi* Leaves.

GCMS test of *Mimusops Elengi* leaves

Acq Time: 03-02-2025 07:29:00

Operator : Dilution

Instrument Name: GCMS

Table 5, a chemically varied composition is revealed by the GC-MS analysis, suggesting the existence of several bioactive chemicals. Because of its moisturising and antioxidant qualities, squalene (19.84% area) is a key component that is frequently utilised in dietary supplements, medications, and cosmetics. The food sector may find use for benzoic acid, 4-ethoxy-, ethyl ester (26.20% area) as a flavouring or preservative. Numerous fatty acid esters, such as derivatives of hexadecanoic acid, indicate emollient qualities that are advantageous for use in moisturizers, personal care products, and medication formulations. Diphenyl sulfone (6.91% area), which is frequently found in medicines and polymers, suggests possible industrial uses.

RT	Compound Name	CAS#	Formula	Area	Match Score	Area% - T	Area% - M
5.2204	Phosphinic acid, diethyl-, methyl ester	100306-05-5	C5H13O2P	3315	77.5	0.22	0.83
5.524	1H-Tetrazol-5-amine	4418-61-5	CH3N5	10075	81.9	0.67	1.02
6.1759	delta.-Valerolactam, diethylboryl-	100162-35-6	C9H18BNO	1359	57.9	0.09	0.99
6.7548	(R)-(+)-1-Phenyl-1-propanol	1565-74-8	C9H12O	9276	80.6	0.61	6.35
6.9156	Benzoic acid, ethyl ester	93-89-0	C9H10O2	1805	95.4	0.12	1.17
7.1202	4-Hydroxy-3-(2-methyl-2-propenyl) aminobenzoate (ester)	94-15-5	C11H13NO3	5189	67.4	0.34	1.3
8.0423	4-Acetoxy-3-methoxystyrene	46316-15-8	C11H12O3	2006	81.4	0.13	1.32
8.1534	Benzene, 1,3,5-trimethyl-2-propyl-	4810-04-2	C12H18	1601	58.5	0.1	0.98
8.2645	ortho-Hydroxypropiophenone	610-94-8	C9H10O2	316	58.5	0.02	0.09
8.4645	Benzene, 1,3,5-trimethyl-2-propyl-	4810-04-2	C12H18	51348	84.8	3.38	2.88
9.0978	3-Pentanone	96-22-0	C5H10O	400	67.2	0.03	0.2
9.1553	2',4'-Dihydroxy-3'-methylpropiophenone	610-94-8	C10H12O3	1300	83.6	0.09	0.68
9.6199	Benzene, 1-(1-ethylpropyl)-4-propyl-	54789-16-3	C12H18	5343	64.9	0.35	1.03
9.7155	Pentanoic acid, 5-hydroxy-, 2,4-di-t-butylphenyl ester	16623-87-7	C15H22O3	1726	77.8	0.11	0.72
9.7735	3-Methyl-2-butanone, 4-t-butylidimethylsilyloxy-	19145-96-0	C11H24OSi	3934	96.2	0.26	1.87
9.8866	Benzoic acid, 4-ethoxy-, ethyl ester	23676-09-2	C11H14O3	397900	95.7	26.2	13.72
10.6087	Butanal, 3-hydroxy-	107-89-1	C4H8O2	2863	69.5	0.19	0.72
10.997	Inositol, 1-deoxy-	21015-40-5	C6H12O5	883	62.6	0.06	0.24
11.5631	1,2,4-Triazin-5(2H)-one, 3,4-dihydro-3-thioxo-	3636-63-5	C3H3N3OS	2216	65.2	0.15	0.52
11.6841	(+)-N-Benzyl-alpha-methyl-N-nitrosobenzylamine	21891-82-1	C15H16N2O	660	52.0	0.04	0.19
12.1241	Dialkylsilyloxysilane	118901-81-5	C6H18OSi2	960	51.9	0.06	0.24
12.1244	Butan-2-one, 3-(2-ethynyl)((isopropyl)amino-	339950-58-8	C10H17NO	2951	56.1	0.19	0.52
12.2964	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	19687-22-0	C19H38O2	2329	52.1	0.15	0.67
12.986	Diphenyl sulfone	127-63-9	C12H10O2S	104928	95.7	6.91	7.47
13.679	3-Methylbut-2-enoic acid, 4-methoxyphenyl ester	100037-59-5	C12H14O3	1182	63.6	0.08	2.69
13.975	(R)-(+)-14-Methyl-8-hexadecyn-1-ol	64566-18-3	C17H32O	30230	71.4	1.98	1.96
14.1194	Methyl stearate	112-61-8	C19H38O2	4659	70.6	0.3	1.17
14.1972	1,4-Tetradecanediol	18912-64-7	C14H30O2	10276	97.6	0.68	6.61
14.3416	2-Butenoic acid, 2-methoxy-3-methyl-, methyl ester	56009-32-6	C7H12O3	10490	58.4	0.68	2.64
14.5416	Succinic acid, di(3,5-difluorophenyl) ester	100358-04-1	C16H10F4O4	4	51.9	0.0	0.05
15.1415	1-Penten-3-one, 2-methyl-	25041-03-0	C6H10O	4	51.9	0.0	0.05
15.3304	Cyclohexanamine, 1-allyl-N-(2-furfuryl)-	24529-02-0	C14H21NO	1212	54.0	0.08	0.32
15.6526	Hexanedioic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester	103-23-2	C22H42O4	5140	90.3	0.34	4.5
16.1192	Hydrazine, heptyl-	2656-72-6	C7H18N2	4147	52.3	0.27	0.37
16.3525	Hexadecanoic acid, 2-hydroxy-1-(hydroxymethyl)ethyl ester	23470-00-0	C19H38O4	67349	82.1	4.37	16.92
16.4825	Phthalic acid, di(2-propylpentyl) ester	100037-89-5	C24H38O4	8826	90.5	0.57	2.22
17.3057	Carbonic acid, neopentyl cyclohexylmethyl ester	100037-95-8	C12H22O3	5732	85.2	0.37	5.22
17.4301	Octadecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester	1323-83-9	C21H42O4	25259	59.5	1.64	2.97
17.5412	1,3-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester	137-32-2	C24H38O4	8127	96.8	0.53	5.63
19.3523	Squalene	111-02-4	C30H50	305511	95.1	19.84	76.78
20.3743	Vitamin E	59-02-9	C29H50O2	9114	58.7	0.59	2.29

Table 5: GCMS analysis of fresh *Mimusops Elengi* leaves.

Derivatives of isositol and butanol indicate possible biological activity, which could support functional or therapeutic uses. Chemical variety is demonstrated by the large range of retention times (5.2min to 20.3min), which exhibit both volatile and non-volatile components. High match scores (>80) increase the compound identification's dependability. The sample's organic acids and esters suggest potential antibacterial and preservation qualities. The discovery of plasticizers, or esters of hexanedioic acid, raises the possibility of their industrial significance.

The presence of phytochemicals or chemical intermediates with therapeutic value is indicated by triazinone and nitrogen-based molecules. It is well known that methyl stearate and fatty acid methyl esters are used in surfactants, lubricants, and biodiesel. The existence of both aromatic and aliphatic molecules indicates a wide range of chemical functions that are relevant to different businesses. The sample exhibits potential uses in industrial manufacturing, medicines, cosmetics, and food preservation due to its varied chemical composition.

Squalene is identified as a major bioactive ingredient in both the methanolic extract from [15], in Solid State Technology and the GC-MS study of fresh *Mimusops elengi* leaves (Table 4), confirming the plant's traditional therapeutic applications. Although the larger chemical profile in table 4, which includes alcohols, esters, and vitamin E, indicates more pharmacological potential, poor match scores and possible artifacts call for additional testing. The cleaner profile and antioxidant assay results from the reference study offer a solid standard, highlighting how extraction techniques influence GC-MS results. These results highlight the potential therapeutic benefits of *Mimusops elengi* as well as the necessity of standardized analytical techniques to completely understand its chemical and biological characteristics.

This study reveals a diverse range of bioactive compounds, with significant concentrations of compounds such as squalene, vitamin E, and various fatty acid esters, which have demonstrated antioxidant and antimicrobial activities in previous studies. These findings align with research by [16], who identified similar fatty acids and antioxidant compounds, such as hexadecanoic acid and diphenyl sulfone, in methanolic extracts of *Mimusops elengi* leaves. Their study also found high free radical scavenging activity, confirming the plant's potential for use in therapeutic applications involving oxidative stress. In comparison [17], reported a broader array of terpenoids, including caryophyllene and citronellol, along with hexadecenoic acid, in various extracts, which also exhibited antimicrobial activity against pathogens like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*. These studies, together with the present analysis, highlight the medicinal value of *Mimusops elengi* as a plant rich in bioactive compounds with antioxidative and antimicrobial properties. The common presence of hexadecanoic acid, squalene, and vitamin E across studies further supports the plant's potential in pharmaceutical formulations aimed at managing oxidative damage and microbial infections.

Nutrient Analysis of *Mimusops elengi* Leaves

Table 6, shows that the *Mimusops Elengi* leaves are predominantly made up of carbohydrates (85.7%) with a notable fibre content (16.7%), making it potentially beneficial for digestive health. The protein (0.23%) and fat (0.19%) contents are quite low, indicating it's not a significant source of these macronutrients. It offers modest amounts of essential minerals like calcium (53.2mg/100g) and iron (3.16mg/100g), along with a high level of Vitamin A (136.2mg/100g).

With an energy value of 345.43Kcal/100g, it could serve as a good energy source despite its low fat and protein content. The nutrient analysis of fresh *Mimusops elengi* leaves reveals a high carbohydrate content (85.7%) and a substantial crude fibre level (16.7%), indicating potential energy and digestive health benefits. The leaves also contain notable amounts of Vitamin A (136.2mg/100g), which suggests they may serve as a valuable source of this essential nutrient. However, when comparing the ash content-a key indicator of total mineral presence-there is a significant discrepancy between the current data (6.26%) and findings reported by [18], in which recorded a lower ash content of 3.49% ($\pm 0.27\%$) for powdered *M. elengi* leaves. This variation could be attributed to differences in analytical methods, sample preparation (fresh vs. dried), or environmental growing conditions [19], found a notably high calcium content of 1975.16mg/100g and iron content of 4.71mg/100g in *Mimusops elengi* leaves, suggesting their potential as significant sources of these essential minerals [20], detected the presence of various amino acids in the leaves, which are crucial for protein synthesis and overall plant metabolism.

S.NO	Nutrient	Value
1	Energy %	345.43
2	Protein %	0.23
3	Carbohydrate %	85.7
4	Total Fat %	0.19
6	Crude Fiber %	16.7
7	Calcium mg/100g	53.2
8	Iron mg/100g	3.16
9	Vitamin A mg/100g	136.2
10	Moisture %	7.62
11	Ash %	6.26

Table 6: Nutrient analysis of fresh *Mimusops Elengi* leaves.

People have used medicinal plants for therapeutic purposes throughout history, and the main sources of remedies have been plants, minerals, and animals. Among the biological effects of the components of *Mimusops Elengi* leaves are antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-diabetic qualities. It was found that the methanolic extracts from the leaves of the ornamental plant *Mimusops elengi* L. could both considerably reduce inflammation and scavenge free radicals, which are important for a variety of bodily metabolisms. This intriguing source has importance in the food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries as well as potential applications as potent antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents.

The results of this investigation show that *M. elengi* leaf extracts have strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Measuring the inhibition of α -amylase, which hydrolyzes complex carbs into smaller polysaccharides, can reveal antidiabetic efficacy. The findings demonstrated that the anti-diabetic medication significantly reduced the activity of the α -amylase enzyme, with the dried *Mimusops Elengi* leaves showing the greatest reduction at 250 μ g/ml, or 65.33 per cent. It offers both macro-nutrients and micro-nutrients, such as high fibre, vitamin A, Calcium, and iron and is low in fat. The GCMS analysis also represents that the *mimusops elengi* leaves have a good amount of bioactive compounds like squalene, ethyl ester, etc., *Mimusops elengi* leaves are being optimised for therapeutic analysis in order to maximise their potential for both economic and medicinal use. This includes promoting sustainable resource use, recognizing the

development of nutrient-dense plant-based health products, and aiding in the validation of traditional medicine. In addition to increasing the plant's commercial worth, this strategy may boost regional economies and encourage the preservation of biodiversity.

Statement of the Problem Addressed and Originality of the Approach

This study tackles the rising demand for natural solutions to fight chronic health issues like inflammation, oxidative stress, and diabetes, which affect millions worldwide. It focuses on *Mimusops elengi*, a plant long used in traditional medicine, to scientifically confirm its healing benefits. The unique approach combines lab tests to check the plant's leaves for anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-diabetic effects, along with advanced GC-MS analysis to identify active compounds and nutrient profiling using the AOAC method. This blend of traditional wisdom and modern science offers a thorough way to uncover the plant's health and nutritional benefits.

Contribution of the Work to Create a New Knowledge in the Field

This study adds new knowledge by exploring the powerful compounds in *Mimusops elengi* leaves, like squalene, diphenyl sulfone, and fatty acid esters, which show strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-diabetic effects. Using GC-MS analysis, we identified these compounds, and nutrient tests revealed the leaves are rich fiber, and vitamin A. These discoveries deepen our understanding of the plant's health and nutritional benefits. By performing better than standard drugs like diclofenac and acarbose in some tests, the plant shows promise as a natural alternative, contributing to advancements in plant-based medicine and functional foods.

Relevance of the Work to Advance Research and Impact of the Food Science and Technology

This research highlights the exciting potential of *Mimusops elengi* leaves as a rich source of nutrients and bioactive compounds for creating healthier foods, supplements, and medicines. With high fiber, lots of vitamin A, and low fat, these leaves could be used to develop products that boost wellness. The findings inspire more studies on how to best extract these benefits and create plant-based health products, while also promoting sustainable use of natural resources. By blending traditional medicinal plants into modern food and health industries, this work supports biodiversity and opens up economic possibilities in areas where the plant grows abundantly.

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